

ANALYSIS OF TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY AND PROFITABILITY MATRIX OF BANKS BY HMTFP AND FPTFP

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ABSTRACT

TFP is broadly viewed as a standout amongst the most essential apparatuses of examination for the components that have potential effect on the supply side. The strategy for estimation like MPI started by further created by Fare and Lovell (2012) and different deteriorations of profitability measures for MPI presented by Simar and Wilson (2012) and HMTFP list, FPTFP record presented by mentioned O'Donnell in the literature (2008) are required to measure TFP of banks crosswise over various economies. There have been unmistakable utilizations of MPI in the managing an account industry itself Reserve Bank of India, 2008; On the other hand, the HMTFP approach incorporates diverse disintegrations of record into unadulterated specialized efficiency, scale efficiency, blend efficiency, and so forth to enhance the strength and affectability of the outcomes under the procedure.

Keyword: HMTFP, MPI, FPTFP, Profitability Matrix, Productivity.

1.INTRODUCTION

These changes fundamentally have made individual banks in India advertise rivalry oriented and call for development in their execution so managing an account area can withstand with the powers of rivalry and flourish in the evolving condition. In any case, there has been restricted discourse in the accessible writing about the efficiency picks up utilizing distinctive methodologies in the event of banks in India since money related changes Against this background, the measurement of dimension of efficiency of keeping money division and its disintegration into different parameters have turned into the focal point of enthusiasm for the chiefs, scientists and arrangement producers. Efficiency and profitability investigation has essential repercussions for the money related organizations as well as for the administrative experts and at last for the general public .What's more, the efficiency measures can execute as chief marker for developing qualities and shortcomings of the saving money framework and may empower the arrangement creators and controllers to make proper strides as and when fundamental.

2.ESTIMATES FOR HMTFP APPROACH

Despite the fact that, writing on the measurement of efficiency and profitability of business banks gives whirlwind of studies which have for the most part focused on utilizing the development bookkeeping approach accept that assets are utilized proficiently and TFP development can just radiates the innovative change fuses progressively sensible non-unbiased moving generation boondocks What's more, DEA, a non-parametric methodology based MPI to assess execution of DMUs Notwithstanding, it is to be featured that extremely sparse thought has been paid to appraise the TFP of business banks utilizing another measure observed to be multiplicatively entire, i.e., HMTFP records and FPTFP files .

In this unique situation, an endeavor has been made to inspect TFP via cautiously investigating the execution of business banks in India amid post-deregulation period. This will give answer with respect to the general effect of money related deregulation and advancement on TFP of business banks in India and how the administrative changes have influenced the profitability of banks under various possessions. Also, to investigate the idea of efficiency changes over the period, a test for the level of likeness between MPI, FPTFP and HMTFP has been evaluated. The real explanations for the utilization of these three unique measures are the nearness of a few traps in the utilization of MPI including (a) TFP properties are kept up under steady returns to scale (CRS) and inadequacies show up within the sight of variable returns to scale (VRS) which generally speaks to the genuine innovation (b) there is probability

of having infeasible outcomes (Glass and McKillop, 2000; Yoruk and (c) DEA approach for assessing separation capacities while developing Malmquist lists is hazardous (d) The inborn issue with the standard Malmquist is that separation to the boondocks is thought little of if most proficient DMU inside the populace is excluded in the example and investigation in such circumstance prompts one-sided estimations. Then again, HMTFP and FPTFP are free from any presumptions concerning DMU streamlining conduct, the structure of business sectors, or returns to scale for a different inputs and yields case. It additionally gives a chance to break down efficiency changes into three unique measures for example specialized efficiency, scale efficiency and, 2012a)mix.Through efficiency these disintegrations, the investigation will have the capacity to recognize the wellsprings of enhancement or crumbling in the profitability dimension of business banks in India amid the period under the examination.

3.COMPONENTS OF FPTFP AND HMTFP

Input oriented Technical Efficiency (ITE): It is measured as the variety between watched TFP and most extreme TFP that is attainable while holding the input blend, yield blend and yield level settled. The bend going through focuses B and D speaks to the boondocks of blend confined generation potential outcomes set (allude Figure 1.2). It is named confined as it just incorporates input and yield total vectors, which can be composed as scalar products of x_t and y_t . As such, ITE is a proportion measure of the flat separation from indicate A point B.

$$ITE_{n0} = \text{Slope } OA - \text{Slope } OB$$

Input oriented Scale Efficiency (ISE): It is the difference between TFP at a technically-efficient point and the maximum TFP that is possible while holding the input and output mixes fixed but allowing the levels to vary. The movement from point B to D represents this particular measure of efficiency.

$$ISE_{n0} = \text{Slope } OB - \text{Slope } OD$$

Point D refers as the point of mix-invariant optimal scale (MIOS). Thus, the DMU that operate at the point D would be having most productive scale size (MPSS). In other words, the ISE under input oriented scale efficiency model evaluates the productivity of an observed input-output bundle relative to that of the technically optimal scale or MPSS (Pantziou et al., 2011).

Residual Mix Efficiency (RME): It is evaluated by drawing out difference between maximum TFP possible on a mix-restricted frontier and the maximum TFP possible when input and output mixes (and levels) can vary. This measure of efficiency is represented as a movement from point D to point E.

$$RME_{n0} = \text{Slope OD} - \text{Slope OE}$$

The curve that passes through point E is the frontier of an unrestricted production possibilities set that is there are no restrictions on in in this perspective as the movement from point D to E is a movement from an optimal point on a mix-restricted frontier to an optimal point on a mix-unrestricted frontier. Therefore, difference in TFP is essentially a mix-effect. The term residual is used as this movement may also involve change in scale and when comparing TFP at an observed point (point A) with TFP at the point of maximum productivity (point E), RME is the component that remains after accounting for pure technical and scale efficiency effects. The movement from the point B to point E may also be analysed with another route which includes:-

Input oriented Mix Efficiency (IME): It measures difference between TFP at a technically-efficient point on the mix-restricted frontier and the maximum possible while holding the output level fixed. This measure of efficiency is represented by the Figure 1.2 as a movement from point B to point U.

$$IME_{n0} = \text{Slope OB} - \text{Slope OU}$$

Residual Input oriented Scale Efficiency (RISE): It measures the difference between TFP at a technically and mix-efficient point and TFP at the point of maximum productivity. The term scale is used as any movement around an unrestricted production frontier is a movement from one mix-efficient point to another, so any improvement in TFP is essentially a scale effect. However, the term residual is also used because even though all the points on the unrestricted frontier are mix-efficient, they may nevertheless have different input and output mixes. Thus, a measure of scale efficiency may essentially contain a residual mix effect. This measure of efficiency is represented by the Figure 1.2 as a movement from point U to point E.

$$RISE_{n0} = \text{Slope OU} - \text{Slope OE}$$

TFP Efficiency (TFPE) measures the difference between observed TFP and maximum TFP that is possible using the available technology. This measure of efficiency is represented by the Figure 6.2 as a

movement all the way from point A to point E. $TFPE_{n0} = TFP_{n0} - TFP_0^* = \text{Slope OA} - \text{Slope OE}$ where TFP_0^* denotes the maximum TFP possible using the technology available in period 0. Thus, Figure 3.2 represents the following two out of many path ways from point A to E:-

$$TFPE_{n0} = TFP_{n0} - TFP_0^* = ITE_{n0} \times ISE_{n0} \times RME_{n0}$$

$$TFPE_{n0} = TFP_{n0} - TFP_0^* = ITE_{n0} \times IME_{n0} \times RISE_{n0}$$

Either of the two equations can be used to evaluate TFP change. The present study uses equation to measure change in the productivity which can be rewritten as:

$$TFPE_{n0} = TFP_{n0} = TFP_0^* \times ITE_{n0} \times IME_{n0} \times RISE_{n0}$$

The same hold for the bank in time period t

$$TFPE_{nt} = TFP_{nt} = TFP_t^* \times ITE_{nt} \times IME_{nt} \times RISE_{nt}$$

Thus,

$$TFP_{n0,nt} = \frac{TFP_{nt}}{TFP_{n0}} = \left(\frac{TFP_t^*}{TFP_0^*} \right) \left(\frac{ITE_{nt}}{ITE_{n0}} \times \frac{IME_{nt}}{IME_{n0}} \times \frac{RISE_{nt}}{RISE_{n0}} \right)$$

The main enclosures on the correct hand side of condition is the measure of specialized changes since it measure the distinction between the most extreme TFP conceivable utilizing the innovation doable in period t, and greatest TFP conceivable utilizing the innovation plausible in timeframe 0. Accordingly, the industry will encounter specialized enhancement or decay as this term is more prominent than or under 1. The second proportion in enclosures on the correct hand side is reasonable measure of specialized efficiency change, including unadulterated input specialized efficiency change, blend efficiency change and leftover scale efficiency change (O' Donnell,. 2010b)

The present investigation won't just advance the current writing yet in addition give an upgraded picture with respect to the execution measurement of business banks utilizing the multiplicatively total list that measures profitability of the banks regarding specialized changes and different other efficiency parts. At long last, the investigation will feature causal relationship among execution pointers and efficiency

change over the timeframe for banks working under various proprietorships in India. The incorporation of board causality as far as managing an account execution isn't generally present in keeping money written works. Hence, utilizing such methodology will be helpful to reveal some insight into the variables in charge of generally speaking execution of banks and furthermore give an understanding to the approach creators in Indian budgetary market for finding the essential driver of decrease in efficiency and deciding the critical worries for advancing security and soundness of the banks.

4.COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF HMTFP WITH MPI AND FPTFP APPROACH

For an extra understanding and to formally test the level of comparability between the Malmquist, Fare-Primont and the Hicks-Moorsteen efficiency lists, a near investigation for profitability change utilizing these methodologies has been readied. Be that as it may, no such investigation is accessible in the writing which demonstrates relative examination of these records. Yet, few examinations are accessible in the managing an account literary works which thinks about MPI and HMTFP lists. The investigation by Bjurel et al. (1998) detailed the minor contrasts in both records though Sioes and Maques (2012) additionally affirmed minor deviations in normal vales for the brief time frame. Nonetheless, the commitment by Kerstene and Woestyne (2014) investigated the impact of unequal and adjusted board information utilizing both lists and inferred that MPI measures TFP understandings under consistent returns to scale and it is protected and shrewd to utilize HMTFP approach for estimating the TFP measurements. Following Bjurek et al. (1998), the ongoing writing has plainly settled that the MPI has no TFP understanding when all is said in done, while the Hicks– Moorsteen file has a TFP interpretation, 2012a). (O'Don looking into the setting of restricted observational proof, the commitment attempted to fill void and examinations these disseminations of profitability change under the VRS innovation determination. Figure 1.2, 1.2 and 1.3 contains the essential measurements for both the Malmquist and Hicks-Moorsteen efficiency lists. The bank-wise efficiency examination features that open part banks, private division banks and outside area banks are delineating close relationship of the both MPI and HMTFP file while the FPTFP score for banks recorded separations among the files. Furthermore, it has been discovered that HMTFP list approach shows critical variety in profitability change in all the three possession gatherings. This affirms the nearness of intense challenge and great sound tasks among the banks. Such varieties are observed to be more in every one of the banks under various proprietorships delineating the nearness of solid challenge to make due in current business condition. Moreover, the vacillations experienced by banks'dTFP score is because of development or

combination techniques, for example, mergers received by banks at different phases of monetary changes amid post-deregulation period. The discoveries substantiated with Cuesta and Orea (2002) likewise discovered quick profitability decay for sparing banks engaged with mergers, trailed by huge increments. In the present observational application, these variances are uncovered through noteworthy decay in making up for lost time impacts.

In any case, it has been seen that adjustment in efficiency score for the HMTFP record shows up on higher side for PSBs and PrSBs though, FSBs encounters reverse translations, recommending banks having the upside of household field. This thusly may make extreme dimension of aggressive condition for FSBs to improve their dimension of execution. Additionally, these adjustments in FSBs are in accordance with the consequences of Illueca et al. (2009) wherein it has been expressed that extension outside their unique markets can acquire vacillations efficiency gains. In light of exchange, it tends to be affirmed that MPI approach gives somewhat unfaltering outcomes to efficiency development and then again, HMTFP approach gives much clear elucidation to profitability change among business banks in India. Notwithstanding, while at the same time making the relative investigation of the FPTFP scores, it has been seen that FPTFP approach gives more variety in the profitability estimates than the other two methodologies. It turns out to be obvious from the watched estimations of FPTFP approach in the Figure 1.1,1.2 and 1.3 that development in efficiency change for banks segment has been experienced, yet but with larger amount of varieties, prompting the indication of doubt and less dependability for the said measure than alternate methodologies. It is additionally anticipated that that increasingly connected research should be made in setting of HMTFP approach which endures less issues and has all the more clear understandings for TFP.

The measurements for all the three lists are somewhat unique and it turns into an open inquiry, regardless of whether these distinctions are measurably huge or not. Be that as it may, no such tests are accessible in writing in this unique situation (Kerstens and Woestyne, 2014). Be that as it may, these measurements appear to be fairly powerful over the VRS innovation detail yet such example level outcomes may conceivably shroud a great deal of clashing outcomes at the dimension of individual perceptions. Along these lines, it winds up imperative to report Malmquist, Fare-Primont and Hicks-Moorsteen files examination as far as proportions over the timeframe and crosswise over banks in various proprietorships.

The outcomes are deciphered in such a way, to the point that in the event that the proportion (MPI/HMTFP or FPTFP/HMTFP) surpasses by solidarity, the record referenced in the numerator portrays overestimated results for separate efficiency change and its unified parts and the other way around. Right off the bat, it has been seen that by and large the input oriented MPI demonstrates overestimated results over the timeframe for business banks in India as the proportion gives off an impression of being more than solidarity amid the investigation time frame. Along these lines, makes question mark regarding what degree the MPI can estimated the Hicks-Moorsteen profitability list with clear understanding for efficiency development. Then again, being multiplicatively entire list, the Fare-Primont TFP list additionally demonstrates overestimation of results for open, private and remote division banks in India.

Along these lines, certain ends hops out of the exchange, first all the three files appear to differ on the nature and dimension of efficiency changes over the examples. Second, there seem certain similitudes and also varieties in the dimension of aggregate factor profitability for the banks at gathering level over the timeframe.

To create the appraisal progressively intelligent, a unit shrewd investigation has given moderately understandable picture pretty much all the three records. Figure 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 thinks bank-wise estimates for the adjustment in efficiency levels. The graphical examination invests with the end that MPI and FPTFP are overestimating the outcomes for various possessions aside from and hence, authenticating the nonappearance of satisfactory measure of rivalry among the banks working under various proprietorship while making transformation of their individual inputs into yields.

5.TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY AND PROFITABILITY MATRIX

Figure 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 gives efficiency benefit network showing the connection between the dTFP scores and the dimension of gainfulness in 62 booked business banks (26 open area banks, 16 private division banks and 20 remote segment banks) in India with four particular quadrants. To develop the grid, the examination thinks about normal estimations of both efficiency and benefit under various possessions. The normal estimation of dTFP has all the earmarks of being 0.960, 0.985 and 0.970 for PSBs, PrSBs and FSBs. Then again, the normal estimation of 0.174, 0.331 and 0.292 has been knowledgeable about terms of benefit for the particular bank bunches in India.

Figure 1.1: DEA Malmquist Comparison with FPTFP and HMTFP approach (Public Sector Banks)

Figure 1.2: DEA Malmquist Comparison with HMTFP approach (Private Sector Banks)

Figure 1.3: DEA Malmquist Comparison with HMTFP approach (Foreign Sector Banks)

Source: Authors' calculations

- Quadrant I: The quadrant speaks to those banks underneath the normal as far as both gainfulness and efficiency scores. These banks are being considered as upset or powerless banks or basic leadership units and might be considered as target banks in any potential merger situations in the Indian saving money industry. Out of 62 banks, 6 PSBs, 7 PrSBs and 7 FSBs have been observed to be subsidiary to this quadrant. These banks need developed potential for the enhancement in efficiency and perhaps more prominent benefits, while, they might be most likely under resourced and have absence of aptitudes.
- Quadrant II: The banks situated in this quadrant work with the high efficiency scores yet low productivity, likely because of the horrible condition for the operationsrs.' Theseor'cashba bovines' and out of 62 rSBsbanksand6FSBsonlyarelisted in12this PSBs, quadrant. It is consequently, experienced from the outcomes that a large portion of banks in the Indian saving money industry are working in this quadrant. Be that as it may, enhancement in the benefit of these banks under various possessions in India can be presumably made by selection of various, right mix of administration blend and business systems.

- Quadrant III: The quadrant incorporates the banks having TFP score beneath the normal furthermore, productivity over the average, tionmark(?). the outcomes from the makes sense of feature that off 62 banks, 3PSBs, 2FSBs are recorded under this quadrant. Hence, the banks under this quadrant need to make the ideal use of their assets in order to work at effective generation outskirts. The high benefit of the banks gives a thought that nature inside which the banks are working are ideal one and ought to be treated as the prime contender for the drive in the enhancement in the profitability.
- Quadrant IV: This quadrant contains shaving both the TFP score 'star' and productivity over the normal qualities. The banks partnered to this quadrant are most gainful and most productive banks in the example. Out of 62, 5 PSBs, 5 PrSBs, and 3 FSBs give off an impression of being performing under this quadrant. The star entertainers are reasonable for the other to benchmark and can turn into the good example for the low performing banks in the business. These banks need to upgrade the dimension of profitability further with help of efficiency use of assets, right blend of inputs and yields and endeavor to create at most beneficial scale measure with enhanced and capable innovation.

6.CONCLUSION

The accentuation of this section is to research change in the dimension of profitability, efficiency, innovation of banks in India amid post-deregulation period. For evaluating TFP development, the investigation utilized all around characterized and multiplicatively total HMTFP record presented by O'Donnel (2008). To check analysed the by HMTF Probustness approach, the o contemplate additionally connected a relative examination for the outstanding MPI approach, FPTFP and HMTFP file. Further, the examination used the recently embraced Dumitrescu-Hurlin Panel Causality Tests to explore causal connections by assessing a condition in which change in the efficiency scores over the timeframe is relapsed on slacked estimations of budgetary determinants of profitability and the slacked estimations of progress in the profitability score. The part looks at the patterns in profitability change of keeping money industry amid post-deregulation period and reaction of various type of banks to the change procedure. TFP development has been assessed utilizing input oriented HMTFP display. Two yields and three input particulars have been utilized to report efficiency gains in the banks.

REFERENCES

1. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL ,STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF BANKS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRY, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com), ISSN : 2582-8568, Volume: 2, Issue: 5, Year: May 2021, Page No : 184-194. Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2105025.pdf>
2. Bhadrappa Haralayya ; P. S. Aithal . "Study on Model and Camel Analysis of Banking" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals Volume 4 Issue 11 May 2021 Page 244-259. Available at <https://irejournals.com/paper-details/1702750>
3. B. Haralayya and P. S. Aithal, “A Study On Structure and Growth of Banking Industry in India”, International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management ISSN (Online): 2581-5792 Volume 4, Issue 5, May 2021. Page no 225–230. Available at: <https://www.journals.resaim.com/ijresm/article/view/778/749>.
4. Bhadrappa Haralayya, Retail Banking Trends in India ,International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM),ISSN:2455-6211, Volume: 9, Issue: 5, Year: May 2021, Page No : 3730-3732. Available At http://www.ijaresm.com/uploaded_files/document_file/Bhadrappa_Haralayyaqscw.pdf
5. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, FACTORS DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR : A TOBIT REGRESSION ANALYSIS", International Journal of Science & Engineering Development Research (www.ijsdr.org), ISSN:2455-2631, Vol.6, Issue 6, page no.1 - 6, June-2021, Available :<http://www.ijsdr.org/papers/IJSDR2106001.pdf>
6. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS, International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology ISSN: 2349-6002, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page no: 159 – 164, June-2021 Available: http://ijirt.org/master/publishedpaper/IJIRT151514_PAPER.pdf
7. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , STUDY OF BANKING SERVICES PROVIDED BY BANKS IN INDIA, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com), ISSN : 2582-8568, Volume: 2, Issue: 6, Year: June 2021,Page No : 06-12, Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2106002.pdf>.

8. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANK PERFORMANCE USING CAMEL APPROACH", International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (www.jetir.org | UGC and issn Approved), ISSN:2349-5162, Vol.8, Issue 5, page no. ppg305-g314, May-2021, Available at : <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2105840.pdf>
9. Bodla, B., & Verma, R. 2016 . Evaluating Performance of Banks through CAMEL Model: A Case Study of SBI and ICICI. The ICAI Journal of Bank Management , V :49-63
10. Boitumelo, M., & Narayana, N. 2010 . The Performance of Financial Institutions in Bostwana: A study of selected Banking and Non-Banking Financial Institutions. Asian-African Journal of Economics and Econometrics ,10-15
11. Chaudhari, S., & Tripathy, A. 2013 . Measuring bank performance: An application of DEA. Prajnan , XXXII : 287-304
12. Chavan, J. 2013 . Internet Banking-Benefits and Challenges in an Emerging Economy. International Journal of Research in Business Management , 1 : 19-26.
13. Gani, A., & Bhatt, M. 2013 . Service Quality in Commercial Banks: A Comparative Study. Paradigm , VII : 24-36
14. Goyal, R., & Kaur, R. 2008 . Performance of New Private Sector Banks in India. The Indian Journal of Commerce , 611-11.
15. Goyal, S., Thakur, K. 2007-08. A Study of Customer Satisfaction Public and Private Sector Banks of India. Punjab Journal of Business Studies , 3 (2): 121-127.
16. Idialu, J. U., & Yomere, O. G. 2010 . Stochastic Frontier Analysis of the Efficiency of Nigerian Banks. Indian Journal of Economics and Business , 9 (1) : 75-86
17. Kantwala, A. S. 2014 . Apropos the Soundness of Public Sector Banks. Finance India , XVIII : 1651-1671

18. Khokhar, J. S.2011. Production Efficiency of Commercial Banks in India. Business Analyst , 20 (4) : 8-14.
19. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa and Saini, Shrawan Kumar, An Overview on Productive Efficiency of Banks & Financial Institution (2018). International Journal of Research, Volume 05 Issue 12, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837503>
20. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Review on the Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country (2018). Journal for Studies in Management and Planning, Volume 04 Issue 05, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837496>
21. Basha, Jeelan and Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Performance Analysis of Financial Ratios - Indian Public Non-Life Insurance Sector (April 30, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837465>.
22. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, The Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country With Special Reference to Banks & Financial Institution (april 30, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844432> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844432>
23. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Study on Performance of Foreign Banks in India (APRIL 2, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844403> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844403>
24. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-Finance and the Financial Services Industry (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844405> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844405>.
25. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-payment - An Overview (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844409> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844409>